

Review of Wing Morphology in Fossil and Modern Species of Humpbacked Flies (Diptera: Phoridae)

Mélanie C.M. Herbert¹, André Nel², Brian V. Brown³, Antonio Arillo⁴, Brendon E.
Boudinot⁵, Mónica M. Solórzano-Kraemer¹

¹*Paläontologie und Historische Geologie, Senckenberg Forschungsinstitut und Naturmuseum,
Senckenberganlage 25, D-60325 Frankfurt-am-Main, Germany.*

²*Institut Systématique Evolution Biodiversité (ISYEB), Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, CNRS,
Sorbonne Université, EPHE, Université des Antilles, Paris, France.*

³*Department of Entomology, Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County, 900 Exposition Blvd, Los
Angeles, CA, 90007, USA.*

⁴*Departamento de Biodiversidad, Ecología y Evolución, Facultad de Biología, Universidad Complutense,
Madrid, Spain.*

⁵*Entomology II, Abteilung Terrestrische Zoologie, Senckenberg Forschungsinstitut und Naturmuseum,
Senckenberganlage 25, D-60325 Frankfurt-am-Main, Germany.*

**Correspondence to be sent to: Paläontologie und Historische Geologie, Senckenberg Forschungsinstitut
und Naturmuseum, Senckenberganlage 25, D-60325 Frankfurt-am-Main, Germany. E-mail address:*

melanie.herbert@senckenberg.de or melaniecm.herbert@gmail.com

Appendix 1 – Complement of information of piece SJNB2012-12-10

Specimen SJNB2012-12-10 comes from a large piece that has been divided into small fragments. Each fragment has a letter and each bioinclusion has a catalogue number. Pieces with more than one inclusion are surrounded by a square.

Fragments 12-25, 12-26, 12-27, 12-28, 12-30, 12-31, 12-32, 12-34, 12-35 and 12-36 were used to describe the species *Protoculicoides hispanicus* and *Protoculicoides sanjusti* (Diptera Ceratopogonidae). The reference publication is: Szadziewski, R., Arillo, A., Urbanek, A., Sontag, E. 2016. Biting midges of the extinct genus *Protoculicoides* Boesel from Lower Cretaceous amber of San Just, Spain and new synonymy in recently described fossil genera (Diptera: Ceratopogonidae). *Cretac. Res.* 100(58):1–9.

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Piece SJNB2012-12:

SJNB2012 12-01 Homoptera	(v)
SJNB2012 12-02 Psocoptera	(R)
SJNB2012 12-03 Psocoptera	(S)
SJNB2012 12-04 Hymenoptera Scelionidae	(j)
SJNB2012 12-05 Hymenoptera Scelionidae	(k)
SJNB2012 12-06 Psocoptera	(T)
SJNB2012 12-07 Araneae Lagonomegopidae	(z1)
SJNB2012 12-08 Hymenoptera Mymarommatoidea	
SJNB2012 12-09 Diptera Chironomidae	(o)
SJNB2012 12-10 Diptera Ironomyiidae (wing)	(q)
SJNB2012 12-11 Diptera Ceratopogonidae	(p)
SJNB2012 12-12 Araneae	(n)
SJNB2012 12-13 Hymenoptera Scelionidae	(L)
SJNB2012 12-14 Homoptera	(u)
SJNB2012 12-15 Hymenoptera Scelionidae	(m)
SJNB2012 12-16 Insecta indet.	(x)
SJNB2012 12-17 Thysanoptera	(F)
SJNB2012 12-18 Homoptera exuvia?	(w)
SJNB2012 12-19 Araneae	(z2)
SJNB2012 12-20 Hymenoptera Scelionidae	(z3)
SJNB2012 12-21 Hymenoptera Scelionidae	(z4)
SJNB2012 12-22 Hymenoptera Scelionidae	(z5)

MORPHOLOGY OF PHORIDAE WINGS

SJNB2012 12-23 Hymenoptera Scelionidae	(z6)
SJNB2012 12-24 Diptera Rhagionidae	(i)
<i>Litoleptis fossilis</i>	
SJNB2012 12-25 Diptera Ceratopogonidae	
<i>Protoculicoides hispanicus</i> ♂	
SJNB2012 12-26 Diptera Ceratopogonidae	
<i>Protoculicoides hispanicus</i> ♂	
SJNB2012 12-27 Diptera Ceratopogonidae	(e)
<i>Protoculicoides hispanicus</i> ♀	
SJNB2012 12-28 Diptera Ceratopogonidae	(g)
<i>Protoculicoides hispanicus</i> ♀	
SJNB2012 12-29 Spider web (or fungus)	(y)
SJNB2012 12-30 Diptera Ceratopogonidae	(h)
<i>Protoculicoides hispanicus</i> ♀	
SJNB2012 12-31 Diptera Ceratopogonidae	(a)
<i>Protoculicoides sanjusti</i> ♂ HOLOTYPE	
SJNB2012 12-32 Diptera Ceratopogonidae	(c)
<i>Protoculicoides hispanicus</i> ♂ HOLOTYPE	
SJNB2012 12-33 Diptera	
SJNB2012 12-34 Diptera Ceratopogonidae	(b)
<i>Protoculicoides hispanicus</i> ♂ PARATYPE	
SJNB2012 12-35 Diptera Ceratopogonidae	
<i>Protoculicoides hispanicus</i> ♀ PARATYPE	
SJNB2012 12-36 Diptera Ceratopogonidae	(d)
<i>Protoculicoides sanjusti</i> ♂ PARATYPE	